

MENTAL PECULIARITIES OF CREATING A TOURIST ENVIRONMENT IN BERLIN

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Abstract

The article considers the mental features of the development of tourism in Germany, in particular in the capital city of Berlin. The issues of formation of the tourist environment of Berlin are considered, the directions of the perspective development of the city for the stable popularization of tourism are determined. The structure of the tourist environment of Berlin is analyzed and a concept for the further development of tourism in Berlin is proposed.

Keywords: tourism environment, mentality, Berlin tourism infrastructure.

Introduction.

The study of the phenomenon of the planned development of the tourist environment of Berlin has been observed for 80 years, since the end of the Second World War. Despite the post-war status of the country, countless destruction and socio-economic problems, Germany was able to exercise its right to berethinking and further comprehensive development.

Tourism plays an important role in creating an economically stable country. The triestic objects of Berlin, Munich, Dresden, Cologne and other German cities are known all over the world, annually attracting millions of foreign tourists.

Over the past decades, the Germans have positioned themselves as a tolerant people who have preserved their historical and cultural heritage, their national and gastronomic traditions, as well as their mentality, which are the basis of the tourist environment of the capital city - Berlin.

Methodological basis and research methods.

The methodological basis of this study is the fundamental theoretical provisions and the practical implementation of social geography and tourism studies, incorporated in domestic works: Y. Oliynyk, K. Mezentsev, O. Lyubitseva, M. Pistun, O. Topchieva, O. Shabliya, O. Beydik, M. Krachilom, M. Malskoy and others [1, p.18-24] and foreign scientists: J.Saarinen, S.Gossiling, V.Kruzhalin, F.Kotler, A.Kaurova and others [2, p. 203-215], whose scientific activities are related to the development of tourism in large cities, and regional development and territorial administration.

Presentation of the main material.

At first glance, the life of Berlin, as the largest European capital, seems to be completely calmer than that. This makes it possible to provide comfort for living in architectural proportions, the absence of shady farms and a large number of parking areas in the city center, scattered behind roses and a variety of tree-growing compositions.

But this is a rather calm and moderately noisy city that lives a very dynamic business life, having state administration structures, embassies from around the world, headquarters and representative offices of most concerns, business associations and public organizations located here. It is the most cosmopolitan city in Germany, known for its Prussian learning and religious

tolerance, and for historical, geopolitical and other reasons, rich in the international business community.

Business diversification, joint production of competitive products, export and optimization of tourism services as imports, modernization of equipment and offers, financing of joint tourism projects and other interests of tourism industry entrepreneurs find support in the international cooperation network.

Those who have been in contact with native Germans for some time draw certain conclusions about the mentality:

Orderliness. Most Germans are used to the fact that in Berlin the day off is a real non-working day. That is, everything can be closed, including a club or even a museum. Therefore, entertainment must be planned.

Punctuality. The Germans are economical with any resources, including time. Therefore, a restaurant that opens at 9:05 instead of 9:00 will receive a negative review. But no one will wait for customers even for 2 minutes.

Bureaucracy. Whatever they wanted to open, issue, ask - you always need to collect a package of documents.

Rules. The Germans follow the rules themselves, but they demand the same from others.

The German capital is one of the three most attractive European cities for tourists, second only to London and Paris. Every day about half a million guests stop in Berlin, each of which spends an average of about 200 euros per day. Such results are contained in a study commissioned by the city's tourist office, visitBerlin. The recreation sector employs 275,000 citizens [3, p. 91-101].

One of the main advantages of the city is the developed tourism infrastructure, reports Rata-News. There are about 800 hotels in Berlin for a variety of tastes and budgets: from budget churches to five-star luxury hotels. From January to June 2019, they hosted more than 11 million foreign guests, which is 11% more than in the same period last year. The cost of a double room is on average 75 euros, the cost of living in a hostel starts from 12 euros [4, p. 137-147].

One of the most attractive sides of Berlin for tourists is shopping: the city's shops offer a huge variety of goods at reasonable prices.

Developed transport links also play their role in the growth of the tourist flow. Berlin is easy to reach from anywhere in the world, a large number of air discounters fly here, and major airlines are increasing their presence. The transport infrastructure of the city is impressive: a) land transport - large comfortable city and sightseeing buses; b) rail transport - S-Bahn (city train), U-Bahn (metro) and regional trains and international trains;

c) river transport - sightseeing ships, boats, yachts; d) non-standard transport - bizarre automated vehicles for 6-10 people, sitting in a circle around a beer barrel or at a makeshift table and contemplating the views of Berlin, enjoy local drinks. Such ease and tolerance of the Germans to tourists allows you to create a positive image of the city and attract more and more people to tourism activities.

And, finally, the guests of the city are offered a lot of bright events and activities: unusual museums and excursions (Museum Island, Ocean Museum, Museum of Photography, Museum of the Brand and others), the Berlinale festival.

At the beginning of 2021, excursions were conducted in Berlin in 21 foreign languages, including Ukrainian (from 10/06/2021). Work to ensure that a Ukrainian-speaking guide appeared in Berlin was carried out for more than one month. For 2022, Ukrainian audio guides can be found in almost all vehicles of bus travel companies and main tourist sites (Charlottenburg Castle, Sanssouci Castle and others).

In addition, Germany is attractive as a business tourism center due to various exhibitions and scientific and practical conferences. Along with France, it is the leader in the number of exhibitions of automotive specialization (out of 64 world exhibitions in Germany, about 11 are held annually). This is due to the fact that the country is one of the world leaders in mechanical engineering, in particular, in the production of cars.

About 60% of international fairs and exhibitions in Europe are held in Germany, where about 20 large fair centers have emerged. The oldest fair centers in Germany are Leipzig, Cologne, Frankfurt am Main, Hannover, Munich, Düsseldorf, Essen. Also in Berlin, the largest international tourist exhibition-fair International Tourisms Borse is held annually [7].

To attract Ukrainians to Germany, the Center offers the following events: fairs, exhibitions, conferences and business trips; "wellness", fitness, health improvement; cultural and educational events.

The experience of Berlin shows that a state interested in the development of the tourism industry should finance the promotion of this industry both domestically and abroad, while funding should be directed not only to promotional activities, but also to in-depth marketing research, increasing information transparency and additional education of workers in the tourism industry, which must meet international standards [5, p.178].

After all, the total number of skilled workers in the tourism sector in Germany is 56% (in Ukraine so far only 21%), which indicates a significant lag of our country from world indicators in the development of the tourism industry.

The main indicators of the attractiveness of a tourist holiday in Berlin: culture (75%), outdoor recreation (59%), city walks (59%), cleanliness (47%), safety (41%), modernity (36%), multi-budget hotels (35%), quality culinary/national cuisine (34%), comfort and accessibility (30%), cosmopolitanism and telecommunications (27%), attractive shopping opportunities (21%), exciting nightlife (17%) and good price-quality ratio (10%) [6].

Germany is the largest emission tourism market in the world, characterized by its specific features, namely:

1. Features of the mentality. The Germans are one of the most traveling nations (the development of neighboring European countries, as well as China, Japan, Thailand, Australia). By the beginning of the XX century, the share of expenses of German tourists amounted to more than 12.5% in their total world volume.

2. Transit nature of tourism. Germany borders on nine states, having convenient transit routes that cross this country. Tourists do not stay in the country for a long time, which affects the number of tourist services, resulting in a decrease in the overall income from foreign tourism.

3. Unification of Germany. With the lifting of the Iron Curtain in 1990, German citizens gained freedom of movement, which made it possible to attract foreign tourists. A noticeable shortage of hotels that meet international standards slowed down the flow of tourists from the eastern lands.

This process has significantly increased the already negative balance of tourism in this country. Even in the modern structure of the tourism sector in Germany, there is a disproportion between domestic and foreign tourism. The main part of the tourist flow falls on the "old lands" of Germany.

4. Non-tourist image. Germany is an environmentally attractive state (there are practically no environmentally harmful industries), where all the conditions for recreation and entertainment are created. The Germans are still atoning for the consequences of World War II.

Therefore, a certain time must pass in order for the image of another Germany to be fixed in the minds of most people - tolerant, renewed, anti-militarist. In addition, unlike neighboring countries (France, Italy), Germany has never sought to create the image of the country as a leader in the tourism sector.

5. Maintenance jitter. In the German tourism market, as part of a study of the capital city of Berlin, there has been an increase in the demand of German tourists for foreign travel for a number of years. The average cost of one tourist for a trip outside the country is about 980 euros.

The average income from one foreign tourist per trip is approximately 1,100 euros (1,255 dollars). Berlin is an expensive city not only for foreign tourists, but also for its own citizens, which is one of the reasons for traveling abroad.

It is logical to develop a strategy for the development of the tourist environment of the capital city, the main indicators of which are:

1. Increasing the economic strength and competitiveness of Berlin. Berlin's functions as a capital and service center as well as an East German labor market with skilled workers are potentials that need to be developed in order to better position Berlin as a business location.

Of particular importance are business-related services, bio- and environmental technologies, research and development, communication technologies (media), telematics and the cultural sector. In addition, the tourism industry is a key driver of urban development. Another direction is the economic maintenance of existing reserves, in particular, to create centers of excellence.

2. Preservation of a socially and functionally mixed city. Different groups of urban society require different social and functional qualities.

3. Support and develop Berlin as a green and sustainable city within the framework of the development of the tourism environment strategy program. Berlin's green qualities are an important factor in the quality of city life and the city's image for both visitors and residents.

Therefore, against the background of increasing competition between cities and regions in different spatial contexts (regional, national, international), a regional perspective is needed to differentiate the above goals and develop approaches to implementation (Table 1).

Table 1

National level		
Tourism policy	Management organization tourism	Napivuryadovi ta community organizations
Level of federal states		
Tourism policy	Management organization tourism	Napivuryadovi ta community organizations
Regional level		
Tourism policy	Management organization tourism	Napivuryadovi ta community organizations
Local level		
Tourism policy	Management organization tourism	Napivuryadovi ta community organizations

The developed approaches to urban development planning are aimed at the implementation of these tasks. Comprehensive strategies should be defined covering the hitherto predominant sectoral and departmental branches of activity.

The future of Berlin will continue to be determined by the changing quality requirements of the existing stock, whether it be housing, commerce and industry, retail, leisure, culture or open spaces. This requires a change in control procedures in the public sector (Figure 1).

The goal of developing the concept is to preserve, stabilize and qualify the existing qualities of a tourist capital city, and therefore adapt them to further changes.

Connections. Science and research, culture and tourism are key advantages of Berlin. They will be used for urban development and image building of Berlin. Additional opportunities lie in urban structural factors such as the polycentric structure, the city center with its diverse functions and unique flavor.

Fig.1. The concept of a promising development of Berlin as a capital city

Thanks to strategic goals, clear rules, and clear priorities and subordination, long-term development opportunities remain open when planning the tourism environment.

At the regional level, new forms of marketing and cooperation should be introduced, especially in the areas of business, science and tourism.

Opportunities for sustainable tourism development in Berlin arise in connection with the demographic growth. To do this, as a strategic reserve, the district potential in the city is needed, which must be ensured by consistent subordination.

The metropolitan city, with scientific, governmental and cultural institutions, is a space of economic opportunity. The historic center, Alexanderplatz and the Western City, as well as areas such as Neukölln-Nord or Friedrichshain and the surrounding area form the inner tourist environment of the city. Different spaces have different functions for the city, their interconnection is a central strategic goal.

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